

Awareness of Dental Arrangement in Orthodontically Treated and Untreated Individuals in Kheda District

Dr. Ridham J. Doshi (Postgraduate Student)

Dr. Rutvi V. Shah (Lecturer)

Dr. Aakash B. Shah (Professor, Head of the Department, PG & PhD guide)

Dr. Bhagyashree B. Desai (Reader)

Dr. Neel A. Shah (Lecturer)

Dr. Ahuti G. Shah (Senior Lecturer)

Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics, FDS, DDU, Nadiad, Gujarat, India.

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ABSTRACT

Background:

A person's self-perception of their dental alignment is a key factor in determining the need for orthodontic treatment. Since such treatment is often sought to improve the aesthetics of the teeth, understanding how patients view their own dental appearance is crucial. So, the objective of current study is to explore the level of awareness of individuals regarding their dental arrangement.

Material and method

The present study was conducted by simple random sampling method; 142 consecutive orthodontic patients from which two groups were formed, 70 patient those who have undergone orthodontic treatment and other 72 patients as control group those who have not undergone orthodontic treatment, was selected from the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics, Kheda, Gujarat, India. Both male (57) and female (85) patients were included. A close-ended questionnaire was distributed among the participants, available in both the regional and English language, to assess their awareness of their dental arrangement. It consists of 15 questions. The responses were analysed to determine their level of self-awareness regarding dental alignment.

Result

Total of 142 samples were collected of which 70 were treated individuals and 72 were untreated individuals. The treated individuals showed significantly higher satisfaction with their dental arrangement (90% vs. 37.5%, $p < 0.0001$) and greater awareness of dental alignment issues compared to untreated individuals ($p < 0.001$). Among treated participants, 88.57% were aware of long-term effects, 92.86% understood about treatment they received, and 78.57% reported improved appearance after treatment, and only 60% attended regular follow-ups.

Conclusion

Orthodontically treated individuals exhibit greater awareness and satisfaction with their dental arrangement compared to untreated individuals. However, gaps in follow-up care remain, emphasizing the need for improved patient education and consistent post-treatment monitoring to ensure optimal outcomes and sustained awareness.

Keywords: Orthodontics treatment, Dental self-perception, Malocclusion, Patient Satisfaction

Introduction.

A person's self-perception of their dental alignment is a key factor in determining the need for orthodontic treatment. Since such treatment is often sought to improve the aesthetics of the teeth, understanding how patients view their own dental appearance is crucial. This knowledge helps orthodontists create personalized treatment plans that not only address the clinical issues but also meet the patient's aesthetic goals and expectations. By considering the patient's perspective, orthodontists can design more satisfying treatment experiences. Orthodontic treatment is primarily designed to correct mal-aligned teeth and discrepancies, leading to improved oral health, function, and esthetics.

Malocclusion is defined as "an appreciable deviation from ideal occlusion."¹ Malocclusion is one of the most common oral pathologies ranked third in worldwide public health dental disease priorities, next to dental caries and periodontal disease². Orthodontic treatment may be requested depending on the person's knowledge and awareness of orthodontic treatment to improve functioning and esthetics³.

An important motivation factor for orthodontic treatment is improved dentofacial appearance. The way individual perceives their own malocclusion is a significant factor in determining the

necessity for orthodontic treatment, which often aims to enhance dental practice⁴.

These studies typically involve the treated individuals and assess their awareness of dental arrangement after completion of treatment. Limited data exists regarding the capacity of individuals who have undergone orthodontic treatment to accurately perceive the outcome of their treatment.

The objectives and criteria for orthodontic treatment are founded on professional standards related to function, aesthetics, and durability. The present study aims to assess the awareness of orthodontically treated and untreated adults about their own dental arrangement, including the aspects such as teeth alignment, occlusion and overall aesthetics.

Also identifies the areas of improvement in patient education and post-treatment follow up to enhance the self-awareness and perception of orthodontically treated young adults regarding their dental alignment.

Material and Method

The present study was conducted by simple random sampling method; 142 consecutive orthodontic patients showing willingness was selected from the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics, FDS, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, Gujarat, India. Both male and female patients were included.

Participants were divided into two groups. Group 1 comprised 70 patients who had completed orthodontic treatment, while Group 2 included 72 individuals who had never undergone any orthodontic treatment and served as the control group. The inclusion of both groups allowed for a comprehensive comparison of the awareness and attitudes towards dental arrangements.

The close ended questionnaire was prepared consisting of 15 questions, first 10 questions were given to both the group among them the first five were the demographic questions about the basic information the name, age, education, and about the satisfaction with their dental arrangement and the subsequent five question was about the knowledge and awareness about the own dental arrangements, focusing on aspects such as gaps, irregularities and tooth positioning, and the last 5 questions were specifically for the treated individuals to check their awareness and attitude towards the treatment, including their understanding of the treatment process, perceived benefits and adherence to follow-up appointments. Questions were given with choices of answers that were easily understandable and brief in manner. The questionnaire was distributed to all the selected participants with prior explanation.

Ethical Consideration:

Clearance from the Institutional Review Board was obtained prior to the commencement of the study. Participation

in the study was voluntary. No interventional procedure will be performed on the participants while collecting the information. No incentives or rewards were given to the participants.

Participants eligible for inclusion in the study were adults aged between 18 and 38 years. Individuals who had completed orthodontic treatment as well as individuals who had never undergone orthodontic treatment were included to facilitate comparative evaluation.

Both male and female participants who provided informed consent and completed the questionnaire were considered eligible.

Participants were excluded if they submitted incomplete questionnaires or if their orthodontic treatment was ongoing or incomplete. These criteria ensured that only participants capable of accurately assessing their dental arrangement were included in the analysis.

Statistical Analysis:

The data was analyzed using MS excel which was used to calculate frequency and percentages. Medcalc version 17 was used to calculate parametric and non-parametric tests. For determining the level of significance, the p value of <0.05 was considered, where the frequency and percentages were calculated, normality of the data was checked after which the appropriate statistical tests were applied. Chi2 test was applied to know the association of non-parametric data.

Questionnaire:

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Name of the patient: _____

2. Age of patient: _____

3. Gender

A. male

B. female

4. Education:

A. Primary

B. Secondary

C. Higher Secondary

D. Graduation

E. Post-graduation

5. Are you satisfied with your dental arrangement?

A. Yes

B. No

Awareness and Knowledge

1. Is there gaps between upper front teeth?

a) Yes

b) No

2. Is there irregular alignment of upper teeth?

a) Yes

b) No

- 3. Do you find the lower front teeth are irregularly arranged?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 4. Do you find the upper front teeth irregularly places?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 5. According to you, are your upper front teeth positioned too ahead of lower front teeth ?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

For Treated Individuals:

- 1. Are you aware of the long term effects of orthodontic treatment on your teeth?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 2. Are you aware of the specific type of orthodontic treatment you received?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 3. Have you encountered misconception/myths about your dental arrangement since completing orthodontic treatment?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 4. Do you believe that there is a drastic change in your appearance after the orthodontic treatment?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

- 5. Do you regularly consult your orthodontist / dentist to discuss your dental arrangement post- treatment?**
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

Result

A total of 142 participants were included in the study, comprising 70 orthodontically treated individuals and 72 untreated individuals.

Details (Table 1):

Summarizes the demographic and behavioral characteristics of the study participants

Education: The majority of participants had completed graduation (70 out of 142; 49.30%), with no significant difference in educational levels between treated and untreated groups (P = 0.1332).

Gender: Females constituted a higher proportion of participants (85 out of 142; 59.86%), with no statistically significant gender difference between the groups (P = 0.3736).

Age: There was a significant difference in age distribution between treated and untreated groups (P = 0.0126). The highest

number of participants belonged to the 15–19 age group (55 out of 142; 38.73%), followed by the 20–24 age group (53 out of 142; 37.32%).

Locality: Urban participants outnumbered rural participants (90 out of 142; 63.38%), with no significant difference between treated and untreated groups (P = 0.5156).

Tooth-brushing Habits: Tooth-brushing frequency significantly differed between the groups (P < 0.0001). Treated individuals predominantly brushed twice daily (54 out of 70; 77.14%), whereas untreated individuals primarily brushed once daily (55 out of 72; 76.39%).

Satisfaction with Dental Arrangement: Treated individuals were significantly more satisfied with their dental arrangement compared to untreated individuals (63 out of 70; 90.00% vs. 27 out of 72; 37.50%; P < 0.0001).

Table 1: Demographic details of patients (n=142)

	Treated (n=70)	Untreated (n=72)	Grand Total	P-value (Derived using CHI2 test)
Education				
Secondary	7	8	15	P = 0.1332
Higher Secondary	20	31	51	
Graduation	38	32	70	
Post-Graduation	5	1	6	
Gender				
Female	45	40	85	P = 0.3736
Male	25	32	57	
Age				
10-14	1	3	4	P = 0.0126
15-19	18	37	55	
20-24	33	20	53	
25-29	15	9	24	
30-34	2	0	2	
35-39	1	1	2	
Locality				
Rural	28	24	52	P = 0.5156
Urban	42	48	90	
Tooth-brushing frequency				
0	1		1	P < 0.0001
1	12	55	67	

2	54	17	71	
>2	3		3	
Satisfied with Dental Arrangement				
Yes	63	27	90	P < 0.0001
No	7	45	52	
Grand Total	70	72	142	

Figure 1: Individual person perception

Figure 2: Examiner view

Knowledge Assessment (Table 2):

About the awareness of treated and untreated individuals. Significant differences were observed in the self-awareness of dental arrangement between treated and untreated individuals across various parameters:

Perception of Gaps: Awareness regarding gaps between upper and lower front teeth was significantly higher among treated

individuals (P = 0.01 and P = 0.03, respectively).

Irregular Arrangement: Treated individuals were less likely to perceive irregularities in the arrangement of their upper and lower front teeth compared to untreated individuals (P < 0.001).

Positional Awareness: Treated individuals were less likely to perceive their upper front teeth as being positioned too far ahead of their lower front teeth (P < 0.001). (Figure 2 & 3)

Table 2: Knowledge assessment among treated vs Untreated (n=142)

		Treated		Untreated		Grand Total		P-value
		(n=70)	%	(n=72)	%		%	
1	Are there gaps between upper front teeth							0.01
	yes	8.0	5.6	21.0	14.8	29	20.4	
	No	62.0	43.7	51.0	35.9	113	79.6	
2	Are there gaps between upper lower teeth							0.03
	Yes		0.0	9.0	6.3	9.0	6.3	
	No	70.0	49.3	63.0	44.4	133.0	93.7	
3	Do you find your upper front teeth are irregularly arranged?							<0.001
	Yes	9.0	6.3	32.0	22.5	41.0	28.9	
	No	61.0	43.0	40.0	28.2	101.0	71.1	
4	Do you find your lower front teeth are irregularly arranged?							<0.001
	Yes	7.0	4.9	27.0	19.0	34.0	23.9	
	No	63.0	44.4	45.0	31.7	108.0	76.1	
5	According to you, are your upper front teeth positioned too ahead of lower front teeth?							<0.001

Awareness Among Treated Individuals (Table 3) (Figure 3):

Awareness of treated individual about the treatment, myths and follow-up. Long-Term Effects: 88.57% (62 out of 70) were aware of the long-term benefits of orthodontic treatment.

Type of Treatment: A majority (92.86%; 65 out of 70) were aware of the specific type of orthodontic treatment they received.

Clarification of Myths: 77.14% (54 out of 70) reported that orthodontic treatment helped clarify myths and misconceptions regarding dental alignment.

Perceived Change in Appearance: 78.57% (55 out of 70) believed that their appearance changed significantly post-treatment.

Post-Treatment Follow-Up: Only 60% (42 out of 70) reported regularly consulting their orthodontist after treatment.

Table 3: Awareness regarding their own orthodontic treatment among treated individuals. (n=70)

		n	(%)
1	Aware of long-term effects of ortho treatment		
	Yes	62	88.57
	No	8	11.43
2	Aware of specific type of treatment you received		
	Yes	65	92.86
	No	5	7.14
3	Did the ortho treatment help to clarify the myths and misconception		
	Yes	54	77.14
	No	16	22.86
4	Do you believe that there is drastic change in your appearance		
	Yes	55	78.57
	No	15	21.43
5	Do you regularly consult the orthodontist to discuss your dental arrangement post treatment		
	Yes	42	60.00
	No	28	40.00

Figure 3: Awareness regarding their own orthodontic treatment among treated individuals. (n=70)

Duration of Treatment:

The treatment duration ranged from 12 to 96 months, with the majority (38.57%; 27 out of 70) undergoing treatment for 36 months. Grouping the treatment duration revealed that 30% completed their treatment within 24 months, while 70% underwent treatment lasting longer than 24 months.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the awareness of dental arrangement among orthodontically treated and untreated individuals in the Kheda district, with a focus on self-perceived dental alignment, satisfaction, and knowledge of treatment benefits. The results highlight significant differences between the two groups, emphasizing the impact of orthodontic treatment on self-awareness and satisfaction levels.

Our findings are consistent with research conducted by Espeland et al. (1991)⁵, which reported that dissatisfaction with dental arrangement is often linked to objectively perceived malocclusions, while mild malocclusions may not necessarily impact satisfaction due to personal and psychosocial factors. Similarly, in our study, orthodontically treated individuals demonstrated higher satisfaction and greater awareness of dental alignment compared to untreated individuals, who exhibited lower awareness of irregularities and gaps. These results underscore the role of patient education in enhancing self-awareness and managing expectations to improve satisfaction with orthodontic outcomes. Furthermore, our findings align closely with another study by Espeland et al. (1993)⁶, which examined orthodontic concerns among young adults treated primarily by general dental practitioners. In that study, treated individuals demonstrated

greater awareness of dental anomalies but also reported higher dissatisfaction due to residual occlusal deviations, with over 50% still requiring treatment. Notably, 30% of treated participants expressed dissatisfaction based on a realistic perception of their dental arrangement. Similarly, in present study, treated individuals were more aware of gaps, irregularities, and forward positioning of teeth. However, despite their heightened awareness, they reported higher satisfaction compared to untreated individuals, possibly reflecting an improved alignment outcome. These findings highlight that orthodontic treatment, when delivered to suboptimal goals or without adequate post-treatment follow-up, may not fully meet patients' aesthetic and functional expectations. Moreover, untreated individuals exhibited fewer concerns, likely due to lower expectations or reduced self-awareness regarding their occlusal status. Both studies emphasize the importance of thorough post-treatment follow-up and patient education to manage long-term outcomes effectively.

In addition, our results corroborate the findings of Hamamci et al. (2009)⁷, who explored self-awareness of malocclusion, satisfaction with dental appearance, and severity of occlusal irregularities in a Turkish population. Their study observed that individuals with severe malocclusions reported greater awareness and lower satisfaction with dental arrangement. Similarly, in present study, untreated individuals exhibited higher dissatisfaction and increased awareness of irregularities and gaps, reflecting the same findings as Hamamci et al where satisfaction decreased as malocclusion severity increased. Hamamci et al. also noted that females had

higher treatment needs and satisfaction decreased with age.

Collectively, these findings emphasize the need for enhanced patient education, realistic treatment goals, and robust post-treatment follow-up to ensure long-term success and satisfaction with orthodontic care.

Conclusion

The study highlights significant differences in dental arrangement awareness and satisfaction between orthodontically treated and untreated individuals in the Kheda district. Orthodontically treated participants demonstrated higher levels of satisfaction with their dental alignment and greater awareness of gaps, irregularities, and positional relationships of their teeth compared to untreated individuals. Treated individuals also displayed better knowledge of long-term treatment effects and reported noticeable improvements in their appearance.

However, gaps in post-treatment follow-up adherence were observed, with only 60% of treated individuals maintaining regular consultations with their orthodontist. This emphasizes the need for improved post-treatment education and follow-up protocols to sustain treatment outcomes and awareness.

The findings underscore the importance of orthodontic treatment in enhancing self-awareness, satisfaction, and aesthetics, as well as the necessity for better patient education initiatives to address misconceptions and promote regular dental care among untreated individuals and also make the treated patients aware about the importance of regular follow ups.

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